

Synthesis and Antimicrobial Activity of Some Di-, Tri- and Tetra-peptides Containing Cysteine and Cystine

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Synthesis of different N-tosyldipeptide methyl esters (V-XI) containing S-benzyl-cysteine, valine, glycine and leucine and symmetrical dipeptide methyl esters (XII-XXV) containing cystine has been achieved employing the carbodiimide method. N-Tosyltri- and tetrapeptide methyl esters (XXX-XXXV) containing cysteine, cystine and glycine have also been prepared using DCC. Copper(II) complexes of these peptides have been studied. Compounds VI, VIII, IX, XIV, XVII and XVIII were active against a number of microorganisms.

CYSTEINE and cystine have been found as constituents of plant and animal proteins and of several peptide hormones e.g. oxytocin, vasopressin, ribonuclease and insulin^{1,2}. The effect of the side chain hydroxyl and amino groups in peptides containing serine, threonine, lysine and ornithine on the formation of copper complexes has been studied spectrophotometrically by El-Naggar and coworkers³⁻⁶. Since the results reported were abnormal, it was thought of interest to synthesize some protected peptides (V-XXXV) including di-, tri- and tetrapeptides of L-cysteine and L-cystine with different sequences. The copper complexes and biological activity of the synthesized di-, tri- and tetrapeptides have been investigated.

The synthesis of peptides with S-benzylcysteine proceeds without difficulty as long as catalytic hydrogenation or reduction with sodium in liquid ammonia is not required. As a result, almost all N- and C-protected derivatives and all methods for the coupling of peptides have been applied, regardless of whether cysteinyl or cysteine peptides were to be synthesized^{3,7,8}.

In the present work the *p*-tosyl group and the methyl ester were chosen for the protection of the N- and C-terminal amino acids because the copper(II) complexes of N-tosylpeptide methyl esters were similar to those of the unprotected peptides and these did not possess any steric effect on these complexes^{3,4}. Moreover, several N-tosylpeptide derivatives were reported to possess various biological activities^{9,10}.

N-Tosyl-S-benzyl-L-cysteine (I) and S-benzyl-L-cysteine methyl ester hydrochloride (II) were preferred as starting materials for the synthesis of cysteinyl and cysteine peptides using DCC and no side reactions were observed. N-Tosyldipeptide methyl esters (V-XI) were prepared in moderate yields (58-71%) using DCC.

The synthesis of symmetrical peptides of cystine presents no problem. Symmetrical dipeptides of

cystine (XII-XXV) were successively synthesized by the reaction of N,N'-bis tosyl-L-cystine (III) with two equivalents of an amino acid methyl ester hydrochlorides or by coupling L-cystine methyl ester hydrochloride (IV) with two equivalents of N-tosyl-amino acid, using DCC. All N-tosyldipeptide methyl esters (XII-XXV) were isolated, purified by repeated crystallizations and chromatographically homogeneous products obtained in 56-78% yields.

Treatment of N-tosyldipeptide methyl esters (V-XI) with 0.5 M hydrazine hydrate in ethanol at 20° (or even at 10°) for 24 hr led to the elimination of the S-benzyl group as benzylmercaptan which was oxidized to dibenzylsulphide. Trials for hydrazinolysis of the dipeptide esters (V-XI) using different conditions, such as 30, 60, 70 and 85% hydrazine hydrate at 5, 10 and 20° in methanol, ethanol, chloroform, tetraline and decaline were fruitless. Some authors^{11,12} also found that the S-benzyl group in other peptides was cleaved by treatment with hydrazine hydrate or during the alkaline hydrolysis of esters when ethanol, methanol and xylene were used as solvent.

N-Tosyltripeptide methyl esters (XXX-XXXI) were prepared by the coupling of Tos-L-Cys(Bzl) (I) or Tos-Gly-Gly (XXVII) with HCl.Gly-Gly-OMe (XXVI) or HCl.L-Cys(Bzl)-OMe (II) using DCC. Synthesis of the symmetrical tripeptide (XXXII) and the tetrapeptide (XXXIII) via the DCC method required two equivalents of Tos-Gly-Gly (XXVII) or Tos-Gly-Gly-Gly (XXIX) per one equivalent of L-cystine methyl ester hydrochloride (IV) and two equivalents of DCC. The protected tetrapeptides (XXXIV-XXXV) were prepared in 54-61% yield by the treatment of Tos-L-Cys(Bzl) (I) or Tos-Gly-Gly-Gly (XXIX) with HCl.Gly-Gly-Gly-OMe (XXVIII) or HCl.L-Cys(Bzl)-OMe (II) using DCC.

The structures of V-XXXV were assigned on the basis of elemental analyses, chromatographic studies, ir and nmr spectra. The ir spectra of all the synthetic peptides V-XXXV displayed characteristic

TABLE 1—PHYSICAL DATA OF VARIOUS N-PROTECTED DI-, TRI- AND TETRA-PEPTIDES CONTAINING CYSTINE AND CYSTINE (V-XXXV)

Compd. No.	Name of the peptide*	Yield** (%)	m.p. °C	R _f (tlc)	[α] _D ²⁵ ***	Molecular formula	Nitrogen %**** (Calcd.)	Found
V	Tos-L-Cys(Bzl)-Gly-OMe	71	79-81	0.95	+15.7(c, 0.1A)	C ₂₀ H ₂₄ N ₂ O ₅ S ₂	(6.24)	6.30
VI	Tos-L-Cys(Bzl)-L-Val-OMe	64	95-97	0.86	+ 9.5(c, 0.3A)	C ₂₂ H ₂₆ N ₂ O ₅ S ₂	(5.85)	5.88
VII	Tos-L-Cys(Bzl)-L-Leu-OMe	62	109-111	0.85	+ 8.2(c, 0.5B)	C ₂₄ H ₂₈ N ₂ O ₅ S ₂	(5.69)	5.80
VIII	Tos-Gly-L-Cys(Bzl)-OMe	86	98-100	0.69	+19.6(c, 0.5A)	C ₂₀ H ₂₄ N ₂ O ₅ S ₂	(6.24)	6.29
IX	Tos-L-Val-L-Cys(Bzl)-OMe	70	121-123	0.81	+13.5(c, 1A)	C ₂₂ H ₂₆ N ₂ O ₅ S ₂	(5.85)	5.87
X	Tos-L-Leu-L-Cys(Bzl)-OMe	58	73-75	0.84	+ 5.1(c, 1A)	C ₂₄ H ₂₈ N ₂ O ₅ S ₂	(5.69)	5.72
XI	Tos-L-Cys(Bzl)-L-Cys(Bzl)-OMe	62	122-124	0.87	+21.5(c, 0.2B)	C ₂₂ H ₂₆ N ₂ O ₅ S ₂	(4.89)	4.99
XII	N,N'-Bis(Tos)-L-(Cys) ₂ -(Gly-OMe) ₂	73	188-190	0.84	+13.5(c, 0.7C)	C ₃₀ H ₃₄ N ₄ O ₁₀ S ₄	(9.11)	8.21
XIII	N,N'-Bis(Tos)-L-(Cys) ₂ -(DL-Ala-OMe) ₂	56	191-193	0.82	+ 9(c, 0.8C)	C ₂₈ H ₃₂ N ₄ O ₁₀ S ₄	(7.79)	7.85
XIV	N,N'-Bis(Tos)-L-(Cys) ₂ -(L-Val-OMe) ₂	73	174-176	0.81	+15.9(c, 0.4C)	C ₂₈ H ₃₂ N ₄ O ₁₀ S ₄	(7.23)	7.35
XV	N,N'-Bis(Tos)-L-(Cys) ₂ -(L-Leu-OMe) ₂	64	190-192	0.80	+24(c, 2C)	C ₃₀ H ₃₄ N ₄ O ₁₀ S ₄	(6.98)	6.99
XVI	N,N'-Bis(Tos)-L-(Cys) ₂ -(DL-Phe-OMe) ₂	59	220-222	0.82	+ 3.5(c, 0.5C)	C ₃₀ H ₃₄ N ₄ O ₁₀ S ₄	(6.43)	6.49
XVII	N,N'-Bis(Tos)-L-(Cys) ₂ -(L-Ser-OMe) ₂	56	212-214	0.91	+14.6(c, 0.6C)	C ₂₈ H ₃₂ N ₄ O ₁₀ S ₄	(7.46)	7.60
XVIII	N,N'-Bis(Tos)-L-(Cys) ₂ -(L-Tyr-OMe) ₂	67	200-202	0.82	+12.6(c, 0.8C)	C ₃₀ H ₃₄ N ₄ O ₁₀ S ₄	(6.20)	6.24
XIX	N,N'-Bis(Tos)-L-(Cys) ₂ -(L-Met-OMe) ₂	74	164-166	0.78	+28.7(c, 0.6C)	C ₂₈ H ₃₂ N ₄ O ₁₀ S ₄	(6.68)	6.71
XX	N,N'-Bis(Tos)-L-(Cys) ₂ -[L-Cys(Bzl)-OMe] ₂	68	179-181	0.69	+36(c, 0.5C)	C ₃₄ H ₃₈ N ₄ O ₁₀ S ₆	(5.82)	5.95
XXI	N,N'-Bis(Tos-Gly)-L-(Cys) ₂ -(OMe) ₂	71	194-196	0.65	+ 7.5(c, 0.5C)	C ₂₈ H ₃₂ N ₄ O ₁₀ S ₄	(8.11)	8.20
XXII	N,N'-Bis(Tos-L-Ala)-L-(Cys) ₂ -(OMe) ₂	70	219-221	0.69	+11.5(c, 0.5C)	C ₂₈ H ₃₂ N ₄ O ₁₀ S ₄	(7.79)	8.98
XXIII	N,N'-Bis(Tos-L-Val)-L-(Cys) ₂ -(OMe) ₂	78	129-131	0.61	+22.5(c, 0.8C)	C ₂₈ H ₃₂ N ₄ O ₁₀ S ₄	(7.23)	7.41
XXIV	N,N'-Bis(Tos-L-Met)-L-(Cys) ₂ -(OMe) ₂	75	166-168	0.59	+14.5(c, 0.5C)	C ₂₈ H ₃₂ N ₄ O ₁₀ S ₄	(6.68)	6.80
XXV	N,N'-Bis(Tos-L-Cys(Bzl))-L-(Cys) ₂ -(OMe) ₂	76	100-102	0.58	+17.5(c, 0.5C)	C ₃₄ H ₃₈ N ₄ O ₁₀ S ₆	(5.82)	5.90
XXX	Tos-L-Cys(Bzl)-Gly-Gly-OMe	54	99-101	0.78	+ 9.8(c, 0.5B)	C ₂₂ H ₂₆ N ₂ O ₅ S ₂	(8.51)	8.70
XXXI	Tos-Gly-Gly-L-Cys(Bzl)-OMe	65	169-171	0.83	+ 7.6(c, 0.4B)	C ₂₂ H ₂₆ N ₂ O ₅ S ₂	(8.51)	8.62
XXXII	N,N'-Bis(Tos-Gly-Gly)-L-(Cys) ₂ -(OMe) ₂	67	209-211	0.88	+ 5.2(c, 0.9C)	C ₃₀ H ₃₄ N ₄ O ₁₀ S ₄	(10.44)	10.48
XXXIII	N,N'-Bis(Tos-Gly-Gly-Gly)-L-(Cys) ₂ -(OMe) ₂	62	180-182	0.78	+18.5(c, 0.5C)	C ₃₄ H ₃₈ N ₄ O ₁₀ S ₄	(12.20)	12.28
XXXIV	Tos-L-Cys(Bzl)-Gly-Gly-Gly-OMe	61	175-177	0.86	+20.5(c, 0.5A)	C ₂₄ H ₂₈ N ₂ O ₇ S ₂	(10.18)	10.20
XXXV	Tos-Gly-Gly-Gly-L-Cys(Bzl)-OMe	54	154-156	0.96	+32.5(c, 0.5B)	C ₂₄ H ₂₈ N ₂ O ₇ S ₂	(10.18)	10.25

*Abbreviations are as proposed by IUPAC-IUB Commission on Biochemical Nomenclature, *J. Biol. Chem.*, 1970, **242**, 6489; 1975, **250**, 3215; Cys = cysteine; (Cys)₂ = cystine; Bzl = benzyl; Tos = *p*-tosyl group.

**Crystallization solvent for compounds V, VII-X, XII-XXXIV = ethanol-water; VI, XI = benzene-ether and XXXV = methanol-water.

***Optical rotations were measured in the solvent, (A) = acetone; (B) = ethanol and (C) = DMF.

****All the compounds V-XXXV gave satisfactory C and H analyses.

bands at 3360, 3280, 3060 (NH, CONH, SO₂NH); 1650, 1560, 1360 (amide I, II and III); 1760, 1720 (>C=O); 1720, 1440, 1270, 1180 and 1090 cm⁻¹ (SO₂NH), in support of their structures. The nmr spectra of all N-tosyl di-, tri- and tetrapeptides exhibit aromatic protons in the range δ 7.6-8.5, the NH amide protons at 5.64 and other protons assignable to aromatic and amino acid residues.

The N-tosyldipeptide methyl esters (V-XI) containing L-cysteine as the N- or C-terminal amino acid in the dipeptide gave blue coloured 1 : 1 complexes with Cu(II) (λ_{max} 620-630 nm). On the other hand, the symmetrical dipeptide methyl esters (XII-XXV) containing L-cystine as the N- or C-terminal amino acid in the dipeptide gave blue coloured complexes with Cu(II) (λ_{max} 610-625 nm; Cu : peptide ratio = 2 : 1).

The tripeptide methyl esters (XXX-XXXI) gave violet coloured 1 : 1 complexes with Cu(II) (λ_{max} 565-570 nm). The symmetrical tripeptide methyl ester of cystine (XXXII) gave violet coloured complex with Cu(II) (λ_{max} 565 nm; Cu : peptide ratio = 2 : 1).

The tetrapeptide methyl esters (XXXIV-XXXV) gave deep red coloured 1 : 1 complexes with Cu(II) (λ_{max} 540-545 nm). The symmetrical tetrapeptide (XXXIII) gave red complex with Cu(II) (λ_{max} 545 nm; Cu : peptide ratio = 2 : 1).

From the above results, it is evident that the N-tosyl-protected di-, tri- and tetrapeptide methyl esters containing S-benzylcysteine form normal 1 : 1 complexes with Cu(II) as has been observed for di-, tri- and tetrapeptides of glycine, alanine and serine^{3,13}. However, the symmetrical di-, tri- and tetrapeptide methyl esters containing cystine form copper(II) complexes with the participation of two copper atoms per one peptide molecule. The symmetrical complexes of cystine peptides behave like two separate peptide molecules and this may be due to the presence of the disulphide bridge in them.

The peptides V-XXV and XXX-XXXV were prepared and characterized for the first time (Table 1). All the peptides synthesized (V-XXXV) gave ir and nmr spectra consistent with their assigned structures. The methods used for studying copper(II) complexes were the same as described earlier³⁻⁶.

Biological screening results: The antimicrobial activity of the synthesized peptides (V-XXXV) was determined using the hole plate and filter paper disc methods¹⁴⁻¹⁷. Tos-L-Cys(Bzl)-L-Val-OMe (VI), Tos-Gly-L-Cys(Bzl)-OMe (VIII) and Tos-L-Val-L-Cys(Bzl)-OMe (IX) were found to possess high antimicrobial activities towards *Bacillus subtilis* (ICC-strain), *Bacillus mycoides* (USSR) and *Bacillus cereus* (NRRL-B-569) at a minimal inhibitory concentration

(MIC) of 10-25 $\mu\text{g/ml}$, and were inactive (at 250-500 $\mu\text{g/ml}$) against *Escherichia coli* (NRRL-210), *Salmonella typhosa* (NRRL-B-573) and *Penicillium chrysogenum*. N,N' -Bis tosyl-L-(Cys)₂-(L-Tyr-OMe)₂ (XVIII) and the corresponding L-Val (XIV) and L-Ser (XVII) derivatives had a marked growth inhibitory effect (MIC 10-15 $\mu\text{g/ml}$) against *Bacillus subtilis*, *Bacillus mycoides*, *Bacillus cereus* and *Escherichia coli*. The remaining peptides were inactive at test concentrations of 250-500 $\mu\text{g/ml}$.

The present investigation revealed that introduction of *N*-tosyl protected amino acid derivatives of L-Val, L-Tyr, L-Ser and Gly in combination with cysteinyl, cysteine or cystinyl moieties gave dipeptide derivatives of improved and specific biological properties. Other pharmacological studies are in progress.

Experimental

Melting points were determined on an electrothermal melting point apparatus and are uncorrected. All thin layer chromatograms (*R_f* value) were made on silica gel-G (B.D.H.) using *n*-butanol-pyridine-acetic acid-water (15 : 10 : 3 : 12) as solvent system and iodine-potassium iodide (20%) as detection reagent. Benzidine, ninhydrin and hydroxamate reactions were used for detection of amino acid and peptide derivatives on Whatman No. 1 paper chromatograms (spot reactions)^{9,10}. The ir spectra in KBr were recorded on a Unicam SP 1200 spectrophotometers. The nmr data in DMSO-*d*₆ were obtained with Varian T-60 A spectrophotometer and shifts are reported in δ ppm relative to internal TMS. Optical rotations were measured in acetone, ethanol and DMF, on a Bellingham Stanley polarimeter using 1 dm tube at 25°.

Tos-L-Cys(Bzl) (I), *HCl.L-Cys(Bzl)-OMe* (II), N,N' -Bis *Tos-L-(Cys)*₂ (III) and $(\text{HCl})_2\text{-L-(Cys-OMe)}_2$ (IV): These were prepared according to literature procedures^{1,9,10}.

Synthesis of *N*-tosyldipeptide methyl esters (V-XI ; Table 1): *General procedure*: To a cold solution (0°) of *HCl.L-Cys(Bzl)-OMe* (II) or any other amino acid methyl ester hydrochloride (0.026 mole) in THF (300 ml) was added Et₃N (3.5 ml) and the solution stirred for 30 min at 0°. The reaction mixture was cooled to -5° and *Tos-L-Cys(Bzl)* (I) or any other tosylamino acid (0.022 mole) and DCC (4.12 g) were added to it successively. The mixture was stirred for 3 hr at 0°, left in a refrigerator at 5° for 24 hr, and then for 24 hr at room temp. The precipitated dicyclohexylurea was filtered off and the filtrate treated with gl. acetic acid (0.5 ml) and set aside for 30 min at 20° to precipitate the dissolved dicyclohexylurea. It was filtered off, the solvent removed *in vacuo* from the filtrate and the residue recrystallized from methanol, ethanol or their mixtures with water. The dipeptides (V-XI) were soluble in benzene, DMF, THF, dioxane and alcohols but insoluble in water and ether. All the dipeptide methyl esters (V-XI) were homogeneous

on tlc, responded positively to benzidine, iodine solution and hydroxamate reactions and gave negative ninhydrin test.

Synthesis of N,N' -Bis *Tos-L-(Cys)*₂-(amino acid methyl ester)₂ (XII-XX ; Table 1): *General procedure*: N,N' -Bis *Tos-L-(Cys)*₂ (III) (0.01 mole) and an amino acid methyl ester hydrochloride (0.022 mole) were dissolved in THF (180 ml) containing Et₃N (2.8 ml), the reaction mixture cooled (-5°) and DCC (4.12 g ; 0.02 mole) added to it. The reaction mixture was worked-up as described for V-XI. The products XII-XX were chromatographically homogeneous (detection with benzidine and hydroxamate reactions).

Synthesis of N,N' -Bis (Tos-aminoacyl)-L-(Cys-OMe)₂ (XXI-XXV ; Table 1): *General procedure*: *N*-Tosylamino acid (0.01 mole) and $(\text{HCl})_2\text{-L-(Cys-OMe)}_2$ (IV) (0.005 mole) were dissolved in THF (85 ml)-dioxane (100 ml) mixture containing Et₃N (1.4 ml). The mixture was cooled to -5°, DCC (2.06 g) added to it and the reaction mixture worked-up as described for (XII-XX). The peptides (XXI-XXV) were chromatographically homogeneous (detection with benzidine, iodine solution and hydroxamate reactions) and gave negative ninhydrin test.

HCl.Gly-Gly-OMe (XXVI), *Tos-Gly-Gly* (XXVII), *HCl.Gly-Gly-Gly-OMe* (XXVIII) and *Tos-Gly-Gly-Gly* (XXIX): The peptides (XXVI-XXIX) were prepared by the procedures described earlier^{20,21}.

***Tos-L-Cys(Bzl)-Gly-Gly-OMe* (XXX) and *Tos-Gly-Gly-L-Cys(Bzl)-OMe* (XXXI ; Table 1):** These tripeptides were prepared from *Tos-L-Cys(Bzl)* (I) or *Tos-Gly-Gly* (XXVII) (0.001 mole) and *HCl.Gly-Gly-OMe* (XXVI) or *HCl.L-Cys(Bzl)-OMe* (II) (0.0012 mole) in THF (50 ml)-dioxane (50 ml) mixture using the method described for the preparation of (V-XI). The products were purified by repeated recrystallization from methanol and finally from ethanol-water, to give chromatographically homogeneous XXX-XXXI.

N,N' -Bis (Tos-Gly-Gly)-L-(Cys-OMe)₂ (XXXII) and N,N' -Bis (Tos-Gly-Gly-Gly)-L-(Cys-OMe)₂ (XXXIII): *Tos-Gly-Gly* (XXVII) or *Tos-Gly-Gly-Gly* (XXIX) (0.01 mole) and $(\text{HCl})_2\text{-L-(Cys-OMe)}_2$ (IV) (0.005 mole) were dissolved in THF (120 ml) containing Et₃N (1.4 ml). The reaction mixture was cooled to -5°, DCC (3.5 g) added and the mixture worked-up as described for XXX. The peptides (XXXII-XXXIII) were chromatographically homogeneous (detection with benzidine, iodine solution and hydroxamate reactions).

***Tos-L-Cys(Bzl)-Gly-Gly-Gly-OMe* (XXXIV) and *Tos-Gly-Gly-Gly-L-Cys(Bzl)-OMe* (XXXV ; Table 1):** These tetrapeptides were prepared from *Tos-L-Cys(Bzl)* (I) or *Tos-Gly-Gly-Gly* (XXIX) (0.01 mole) and *HCl.Gly-Gly-Gly-OMe* (XXVIII) or *HCl.L-Cys(Bzl)-OMe* (II) (0.011 mole) in a mixture of THF (80 ml) and dioxane (50 ml) containing Et₃N (3.5 ml), DCC (2.06 g) using the method described for preparation of XX and XXXI. The products were purified by recrystallization several times from

methanol and finally from ethanol-water. The tetrapeptides were chromatographically homogeneous (detection with benzidine, iodine solution and hydroxamate reactions) and gave negative ninhydrin reactions.

The tetrapeptides (XXXIV and XXXV) were hydrolyzed (6 N HCl, 100°, 24 hr) followed by subsequent chromatography. Both peptides yielded two positive spots with ninhydrin corresponding to glycine and cysteine.

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